

Kotagede heritage city: Identification of conservation and preservation based on community perspective

Kota Warisan Kotagede: Identifikasi konservasi dan pelestarian berdasarkan perspektif masyarakat

Erda Rindasih¹, Muhammad Izzudin^{2*}, Muhammad Baiquni³

¹Centre for Tourism Studies, Universitas Gadjah Mada, Yogyakarta, Indonesia

²Faculty of Social and Political Science, Sriwijaya University, Palembang, Indonesia

³Faculty of Geography, Universitas Gadjah Mada, Yogyakarta, Indonesia

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Corresponding Author:

Muhammad Izzudin
muhammadizzudin@fisip.unsri.ac.id

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ABSTRACT

Kotagede is one of the tourism destinations that has been associated with several sites such as education, history, and culture. On the macro and local levels, policies must guarantee that tourism development does not compromise cultural heritage assets that can provide economic, social, and environmental advantages. The aim of the article is to provide an overview of the stakeholders who contributed to the administration and development of the Kotagede tourist conservation and preservation program, focusing on the United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) standard as a performance indicator. The technique and methods used in this study are observation, filed survey and in-depth interview. The findings indicated that Kotagede had a competitive advantage as a potential tourism destination due to its cultural, historical, gastronomic, architectural, and transportation advantages. The institutional community has been engaged in preserving old structures, promoting tourism, and fostering local economic growth.

ABSTRAK

Kotagede merupakan salah satu destinasi pariwisata yang berkaitan dengan beberapa situs seperti pendidikan, sejarah, dan budaya. Pada tingkat makro dan lokal, kebijakan harus menjamin bahwa pengembangan pariwisata tidak mengorbankan aset warisan budaya yang dapat memberikan keuntungan ekonomi, sosial, dan lingkungan. Artikel ini bertujuan untuk memberikan gambaran tentang para pemangku kepentingan yang berkontribusi dalam penyelenggaraan dan pengembangan program konservasi dan pelestarian wisata Kotagede, dengan fokus pada standar United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) sebagai parameter studi. Teknik dan metode yang digunakan dalam penelitian ini adalah observasi, survei lapangan dan wawancara mendalam. Hasil temuan menunjukkan bahwa Kotagede memiliki keunggulan kompetitif sebagai tujuan wisata potensial karena keunggulan budaya, sejarah, gastronomi, arsitektur, dan transportasi. Serta adanya komunitas lokal telah berkontribusi dalam melestarikan struktur lama, mempromosikan pariwisata, dan mendorong pertumbuhan ekonomi local.

INTRODUCTION

Tourism provides an ideal chance to collect data on the expected number of foreign travelers (Inbound Tourism). According to WTO projections (Rusu et al., 2009), The worldwide tourist population is expected to

reach 1.046 billion in 2010 and 1.602 billion in 2020, including 231 million and 438 million people in East Asia and the Pacific, respectively, and the global economy will earn USD 2 trillion in revenue in 2020.

Cultural tourism, more particularly heritage tourism, is widely recognized as the largest and fastest growing tourist sector on the planet (Timothy & Boyd, 2006). The World Tourism Organization (2018) in (Timothy, 2021) has been reported that about four out of every ten tourists picked their destination based on the cultural attractions available. According to this expanding tendency, the World Tourism Organization projects that cultural travel will rise at a 15 percent yearly pace by the end of the century.

Immediately after the (World Travel & Tourism Council, 2004), countries began reframing the sector after declaring tourism to be a substantial business, the largest in the world. At the beginning of the century, microeconomists Joseph Pine II and James H. Gilmore asserted that industrialized nations' economies had shifted away from brand-based economies (centered on manufacturing and branded products) and toward experience economies (economy based on experience or impression) (Sousa et al., 2017). Between 1959 and 1996, experience tourism boosted employment by 5.3 percent (much more than services expanded by just 2.7 percent or manufacturing by only 0.5 percent).

Many ASEAN member states are in the process of changing to this type of currency. As a result of increasing travel to the free trip destination, Malaysia, the Philippines, Thailand, and even Singapore established a similarity (Liu et al., 2018); (Nugroho, 2017) In the province of Yogyakarta, there has been a gradual transition away from mono-tourism activity (Widayati et al., 2020). When considering tourism in the modern world, two (two) models may be identified: small group mass tourism and large group tourism. Both operate concurrently, and in Indonesia, two distinct kinds of tourism exist.

The concept of sustainable development was created by the United Nations General Assembly's World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED) (Siraj-Blatchford et al., 2016). Sustainable development, according to the World Commission on Environment and Development, is defined as "development that meets the demands of the present without jeopardizing the capabilities of future generations." The objective of meeting their demands is to integrate development with the environment from the first stages of policy formation and decision-making strategy creation through field deployment.

The Federation of Nature and National Parks (1993) in (Edgell, 2019) defines sustainable tourism as "all forms of tourism development, management, and activity that preserve the environment's integrity, social, economic, and welfare benefits of natural and cultural resources that exist for an extended period of time."

Cultural heritage, according to the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), includes cultural heritage sites, historic cities, sacred natural sites, underwater cultural heritage, museums, cultural heritage moves, craft, heritage documentation digitally, cinematographic heritage, oral traditions, language, festivals, religion and belief, music and more, performing arts, traditional medicine, literature, and other traditional attraction. The majority of these assets are intangible cultural heritage (oral tradition, language ability and knowledge creation process, performing arts, festivals, religion and belief, cosmology and belief system of learning and practice, and beliefs and practices concerning nature). In 2003 and 2005, UNESCO designated Puppet and Dagger as an Intangible Cultural Heritage Site.

Numerous countries' success in developing their tourism sectors is based on the development of professional tourism destinations that are integrated sectorally and regionally, have a clear concept, are backed up by a dependable service and service system, and are bolstered by an active, intensive, and focused marketing system and strategy. In Indonesia, the development of tourism destinations continues to face a number of hurdles, including weak sectoral coordination and assistance, as well as cross-regional/regional coordination that has been unable to function successfully owing to regional egos/spirits. On the other hand, tourism developments and global market trends increasingly necessitate the development and management of tourism destinations capable of providing attractive attractions, creative and unconventional attraction management, high-quality tourism experiences and services, and a variety of information-related conveniences. Connectivity, interregional connectivity, as well as various advantages and amenities associated with travel.

Tourism destinations in Indonesia are quite different, depending on the destination's culture. Cultural tourism-based destinations are one of the critical destinations bases that require attention. This is critical, as legacy tourism touches on a variety of topics, including education, history, and culture. Policies at the macro and micro levels of management must be considered, as it is hoped that the growth of cultural heritage tourism will not jeopardize the community's cultural values and will bring economic, social, and environmental advantages. As such, this research aims to add to the analysis of destinations in one of the city of Yogyakarta's most significant destinations, namely the Kotagede cultural arts and heritage region.

Preservation of heritage places is a managerial activity that has a value of biophysical, historical, and cultural sustainability in order to continue accepting changes and progress, maintaining the old asset and ensuring present and future sustainability. The objective of a heritage conservation district is to conserve and develop the region's cultural qualities, which may be quantified in terms of architectural, historical, and social significance. Thus, preserving the past's cultural heritage is not a romantic endeavor, but rather the preservation of the need to examine various facets of life through program participation, economic analysis, and future projections, as well

as to increase the attractiveness of local businesses and develop socio-cultural activities in the neighborhood (Adishakti, 1999). Meanwhile, conservation is a development endeavor that is inextricably related to an economic strategy aimed at enhancing people's and their environment's quality of life. Individuals must have benefitted ethically and monetarily from conservation activities.

In general, these studies share a concern about the inherent value of cultural heritage assets as significant potential tourism resources and, as such, as a factor of local development (Ramires et al., 2018). The dimensions of their tourism development must be managed by heritage destinations. They must establish a balance between boosting tourism and economic growth and protecting artifacts, historical sites, and indigenous cultures on the one hand, and indigenous cultures on the other (Poria et al., 2013). Heritage destinations, on the other hand, suffer unique issues due to the fact that they typically include several stakeholders, limited economic and managerial resources, and a lack of local identity (Morgan & Pritchard, 2006).

Additionally, it is necessary to include the opinions of many stakeholders into the historic tourism-preservation conundrum. As a result, some studies have focused on non-expert perspectives on WHSs, such as the perceptions and attitudes of tourists, inhabitants, and host communities (Bourdeau et al., 2016).

From that explained background, the aims of this study are: 1) Analyzing the conservation and preservation in Kotagede City using sustainable tourism development standard United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), 2) Identify potential local stakeholders as a basis for the development and Kotagede heritage destinations.

METHODS

This study was conducted in the Kotagede region. Kotagede is divided into two administrative districts: Bantul Regency and Yogyakarta Municipal. However, this study is limited to the Kotagede area of Yogyakarta Municipality because to the concentration of tourist destinations in this region. Kotagede is a settlement in Yogyakarta Municipality with 40 RW and 164 RT. Rejowinangun has a population of 40.72 percent, whereas Purbayan has a population of 27.03 percent (Yogyakarta Central Bureau of Statistics, 2021)

The methodology used in this tourism study is qualitative (Veal, 2017; Hillman & Radel, 2018); Since the quantification and categorization of data in recreation and tourism research have repeatedly been criticized for strengthening current knowledge rather than producing new knowledge along the border (Coalter, 2019). Additionally, because tourism is viewed as a social practice, similar to recreation, recognizing the advantages is critical. A qualitative approach is appropriate for this inquiry. Several strategies were employed in this study to collect data and information from appropriate sources.

This study uses both primary and secondary data. Primary data were gathered by observations, questionnaires, in-depth interviews, and documentation. Secondary data were acquired from the literature and from a variety of sources. Purposive random sampling is used to choose the study sample.

The informants and collected data of the research are (1) 18 peoples tourist spot guard used semi-structure questionnaire collecting by field survey and observation, (2) Three head villages of Prenggan, Purbayan and Rejowinangun, and (3) Five Tourist Community Stakeholders, there are, Kanthil Society, Joglo Forum, Community Self-reliance Agency (CSA), Kotagede Documentation Center (KDC), and PNPM Mandiri Pariwisata used in depth interview.

Furthermore, the data analysis uses a descriptive statistic frequency table to simply the survey data on the field where it was collected to identify the safeguards, tourists, and society around the 18 sites doing preservation and conservation. Qualitative descriptive analysis was used to describe and express the perspective of head villages and local tourism community stakeholders about local tourism policy, tourism fund reconstruction sites due to earthquake disaster, tourist attitude and local market due to tourism survived and local festival to attract tourist sustain come to Kotagede.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Kotagede Tourism Attractions

There are 18 sites tourism destination among Kotagede heritage area would be analyzed using sustainable tourism destination standard by UNWTO which shown in table below:

Table 1. Destinations research sites

Tourist Destination Research Sites Selection			
1	Sepingan Palace	10	Babon Aniem dan Legi Market
2	Dhuwur Boharen Mosque	11	Kalang House
3	Bokong Semar	12	Malang Post Security
4	Gilang, Chanteng and Genthong Stone	13	Ngori street
5	Monggo Chocolate	14	Sumber kemuning
6	Between Two Gates	15	Omah Dhuwur
7	The Great Kotagede Mosque Area	16	Silversmith
8	Hestarangga Cemetery	17	Cepuri (Inside Fort)
9	Hamengku Buwono IX Seat Monument	18	Raden Ranga Debris Fort

Tourist, as a critical component of the tourism sector, consists of three distinct components dubbed the triple A. (Attraction, Amenitas and Accessibility). Any item that may be 'sold' as a tourist commodity qualifies as a tourism product.

Kotagede Heritage Conservation and Preservation

The conservation and preservation of Kotagede's legacy were assessed using a variety of indicators, including attraction, accommodation, infrastructure and amenities, and structure. Each element was broken down into several factors. Additionally, each variable is assigned a value ranging from 1 (one) to 3 (three), which corresponds to the lowest to the greatest values. The study's findings are presented in a table of graphs with the results classified into three categories: low, middle, and high.

Table 2. The score of Kotagede heritage sites for the variable attraction

Attraction	Low	Middle	High	
Attractiveness	1	2	15	15
Uniqueness	0	3	15	15
Diversity	3	15	0	0
Spatial and environment	2	14	2	2
Flora and fauna	15	2	1	1
Green adventure	15	3	0	0
Events	0	15	3	3
Total	36	54	36	36
Percentage (percent)	28,6	42,9	28,6	

According to the survey results, 42,9 percent of the 18 Kotagede historic sites are sufficiently appealing for tourism, both domestic and international, 36 percent are sufficiently attractive, and only 28,6percent of the Kotagede heritage sites are not enough suitable for tourism. More precisely, a high score indicates that the region is beneficial for tourism, as Kotagede has an appealing location and distinctive architecture that cannot be found in any other locality. According to Harahap & Rahmi (2019); Hilal (2020)research, the tourist attraction of Kotagede is its cultural and architectural uniqueness related to Octaviano's reseach (2013).

The middle score demonstrates that Kotagede is diverse, has a spatial structure based on Javanese architecture, and has a pleasant setting. However, due to the lack of activities aimed at luring tourists, the Yogyakarta government should host events.

Table 3. The score of Kotagede heritage sites for the variable accesibility

Accesibility	Low	Middle	High	
The quality of the road from origin to Kotagede	0	3	15	15
The quality of the road in the destination	2	1	15	15
The quality of the road to other destination	0	6	12	12
The public transportation mode availability	17	1	0	0
The easy access	0	2	16	16
Comfortable (temperature as the effect of vegetation's in Kotagede)	10	5	3	3
Access to tracking and watching	13	2	3	3
Total score	42	20	64	64
Percentage	33,3	15,87	50,8	

Generally, the majority of Kotagede historic sites are classified as having a high level of accessibility. There is 50,8 percent evidence that Kotagede heritage sites are easily accessible, including the road's condition and ease of access. Study byReknoningtyas in 2016, showed that its related ease to access in Kotagede and a lot of information by websites.

The lowest score indicated that 33,3percent of Kotagede historic sites were unsuitable for strolling due to a lack of vegetation, and tourists were unable to use public transit due to the road's close proximity to civil houses. 15,87percent of it is deemed to be in the intermediate scores.

Another factor to consider while analyzing tourism is the area's infrastructure and facilities. This element is quantified using fifteen variables, including the following: road pad, souvenir store, electricity, cellphone signal, place to stay, entertainment, tickets, hotspot, shelter, children's play area, restaurant, restroom, information map, historical information, and movie / gallery.

Table 4. The score of Kotagede heritage sites for the variable infrastructure and facilities.

Infrastructure and Facilities	Low	Middle	High
Road pad	1	8	9
Souvenir Shop	0	1	17
Electricity	0	0	18
Cellular Signal	0	0	18
Hotel or place to stay	15	2	1
Entertainment	18	0	0
Ticketing (box)	18	0	0
Hotspot	0	0	18
Shelter	8	10	0
Children play ground	13	3	2
Restaurant/food court	14	4	0
Toilet	2	15	1
Information Map	15	3	0
Historical Information	16	0	2
Movie/gallery	15	3	0
Total	135	49	86
Percentage (percent)	50,0	18,15	31,85

According to the chart above, 50 percent of these factors is still in low score, especially for road pad, tourist store, electricity, cellphone coverage, and hotspot area. This result indicated low contribution by local government to maintenance potential tourism in Kotagede as same as evaluation from Reknongtyas (2016), who argue there are lot of facilities adding and upgrading. This result inline with the research conducted by Adhelia et al., (2015); Rosilawati & Mulawarman, (2021) which proving that conservation in Kotagede is still mostly carried out by the community, with limited intervention from the local government.

The middle score is 18,15percent, including the toilet. Indeed, the bathroom is a critical facility for tourism destinations, since it reflects the cleanliness and splendor of the place. As a result, the Yogyakarta administration should construct toilets near Kotagede cultural sites that are easily accessible and usable by tourists. This result same as research conducted by (Noviastuti & Februandari, 2020) that public toilet facilities are one of the things that have a low rating. But, even another facilities had lower scores, there are the highest score (31.85 percent) included a place to stay, a shelter, a restaurant, a playground for children, and an information map.

The purpose of conservation is to protect and develop the region's cultural qualities, which may be identified by the architectural, historical, and social values. Additionally, conservation should focus on any place or historic component that has distinct qualities and is typically accompanied by care and indigenous understanding to maintain it.

Table 5. The score of Kotagede heritage sites for the variable building

Building	Low	Middle	High
Building preservation	2	3	13
Architectural style and structure change	1	17	0
Building character	0	18	0
Preservation cost	1	16	1
Buiding usage	1	17	0
Total	5	71	14
Percentage (percent)	5,6	78,9	15,6

The highest score for building conservation is 15,6 percent, which includes work financed by the Javanese Reconstruction Fund (JRF) and the Yogyakarta government following the 2006 tictonic earthquake in Bantul Regency. This result can be seen in BNSK (2018) and Rahmi(2017)research which identify and evaluating JRF contribution to preserve cultural building in Kotagede.

Numerous buildings designated as historic were rehabilitated between 2006 and the end of 2011. The majority of Kotagede heritage sites (78,9 percent) have received adequate evaluation, but they still require additional improvement and management by both the government and parties interested with Kotagede preservation. Furthermore, MacRae & Hodgkin (2016), described the state of the Bantul building following the disaster in their research.

Community Conservation and Preservation Perspective

Stakeholders play an fundamental role in the tourism destination's growth. Particular stakeholder contributions are made in accordance with their specific roles and domains. Research by Dewi (2013) in Jatiluwih tourism village, Herdiana (2019); Handayani and Warsono (2017) di Karang Jahe Coastal tourism, Kristiana and Nathalia (2019) in Biak Numfor, Suherlan et al. (2020) in Gubugklakah tourism village, Salouw (2021) in Banda,

showed how the important role of stakeholder and in tourism destination development, preservation and conservation.

Numerous stakeholders may be identified in Kotagede, particularly those involved in tourism-related activities.

1. Kanthil Society

Kanthil Society is one of the institutions operating in Kotagede. It was founded on December 31, 1999 at 76 A Kotagede. Kanthil Society provides tourism information in Kotagede guidance and services to each visitor regardless of time limits and as non government agency concerned about local tourist guidance. According to interviews with Muhammad Natsir (the Kanthil Society's chairman), local genuine artisans Kotagede is no longer degraded by huge shops whose ownership is beyond the residents' financial problem. Along with advocating for tiny silver artists, it strives to campaign for homeowner heirlooms that are exempt from earth construction taxes, making administration easier for the roughly Kotagede people. So from this point, research from Anurogo *et al.*, (2017); Arya (2021) also views the importance of developing the silver handcraft industry in supporting the economy of the people of Kotagede.

Kanthil Society determine that the government occasionally preaches undesirable things, such as those who prefer to sell their valuables at home when doing so violates the regulations of the historic house. Kanthil Society also examined the travel agency, concluding that it now treats individuals as things, prompting Kotagede to take shots. Society kanthil is attempting to apply the notion of a win-win situation to every tourist that comes to meet with inhabitants Kotagede, the citizens who are the topic of tourism, in order to ensure that visitors demonstrate no respect. Research from Nurul Hakim (2018) and Puspita Sari & Widiyastuti (2020), also stated about the community aspect in preserving the culture of Kotagede.

2. Joglo Forum

Joglo Forum is a Kotagede-based organisation comprised of several facets of society. The forum's members are mostly the observer Joglo Kotagede Kanthil Society and other aspects. The Joglo forum's activities are limited to the advancement of Javanese culture's art, information services to the community, and service packages.

The historic Kotagede Chess Gatra Space's ideology is one that blends spatial market presence, a palace, a mosque, and *alun - alun* as the central business district. According to sources, development should be the beginning point if Kotagede places a higher premium on characteristics of the historic area that may connect two administrative regions as well as the Yogyakarta Municipality and Bantul Regency.

Kotagede became crowded with tourists for the first time during the Soeharto government, which built Tapaksiring because of the many painters in Bali. However, in the past, Ngurah Rai Airport has not been built, meaning that tourists must transit at Soekarno-Hatta Airport first. Since then, namely in the 1960s, tourism has only been promoted to Kotagede, and starting in the 1970s, the silver industry has begun to be developed as a complement to tourism in Kotagede. According to informant, there are various potential tourism in Kotagede, include 1) history and culture (status and building), 2) the kingdom, 3) gastronomic, 4) arts, and 5) social movement (Former Muhammadiyah movement).

Kotagede development has began in 2009, after the 2006 earthquake, collaboration with the Java Reconstruction Fund (JRF) to reconstruct old infrastructure and dwellings - including relics such as the joglo or *limasan*. JRF formed a Heritage Conservation District Organization in conjunction with local communities, in this case represented by the Community Self-reliance Agency (CSA). The CSA's role is to document the harm and, at a later point, to provide advise on institutional strengthening. This operation is not only carried out at the beginning, but also throughout the post-reconstruction phase, when CSA is tasked with the responsibility of preserving and caring for buildings and infrastructure restored by JFR.

3. Community Self-reliance Agency (CSA)

Community self-reliance agencies (CSA) are scattered across Kotagede's settlements. CSA has developed communities that are scattered across Kotagede by the Heritage Conservation District Organization (HCDO). The Community Self-Sufficiency Agency's mission was to restore values - the noble values of village people, places, and policy decisions, as well as the media, information, and communication center's objectives for urban residents. The members of the CSA, which are mostly inhabited by youths, have actually given their ideas and energy for the welfare of the community.

Budiharto, the Community Self-Sufficiency Agency's manager, noted that Purbayan Village was a pioneering tourism village in 2009 due to JRF's rehabilitation of essentially all of the structures destroyed in the 2006 earthquake. However, ongoing attempts to progressively establish the economic viability of the people of Kotagede's tourist community, sponsored by the PNPM Mandiri, are necessary. Along with its engagement with different public and commercial entities, the Community Self-Sufficiency Agency also offers training for CSA members, bring in trainers and resource persons from local as well as from agencies such as the D.I. Tourism Office. Yogyakarta regularly every 3 months. The CSA's primary goal is to

maximize the possibilities within the community, such as cuisine, craft, art, and religion, so that local residents become aware of and invested in the village's growth beginning with themselves.

4. Kotagede Documentation Center (KDC)

The Kotagede Documentation Center is an institute established by the Kotagede to promote Kotagede's potentials in addition to the Mataram Kingdom's legacy. The purpose of this community is to create and conduct business in the fields of study, documentation, and cultural, social, and environmental development.

The findings of interviews with the chairman of the community, Erwito, the community was founded in the 1970's by activists and young Kotagede believe that at this time period, they were less able to persuade foreigners to come and enjoy the potential - potential that is actually fairly substantial and has existed since their forefathers. In light of these challenges, individuals like as Zubair and Dervish Khudori Charris pioneered the development of the community and drew together all the kids who were previously less productive - youth who possess the creativity and willingness to construct a community.

Their program runs with financial support from a variety of sources, including government agencies and international donors, and its primary objective is to manage the site - cultural sites. One of the foreign organizations that assists in the management and reconstruction of the cultural district is the Java Reconstruction Fund (JRF). The JRF is an international organization founded by governments of developing countries such as Japan, Germany, France, and other European countries.

Along with accompanying international visitors to Kotagede, the KDC also arranges noteworthy cultural events for the larger community, such as the Timpasko Festival (at East Kotagede market), which served as the seed for the Kotagede Festival.

5. PNPMM Mandiri Pariwisata

PNPMM Mandiri Pariwisata is a community organization dedicated to the development of tourism in Kotagede through the coordination of government initiatives such as the National Poverty Alleviation Program, which are directly administered by the people of Kotagede. The scope of operations includes projects that directly impact individuals and are already transforming the lives of a large number of rural residents. Kotagede as a historic region will draw tourists to witness numerous artifacts of one of the major Islamic empires in the past, the kingdom of Mataram, and the public's interest in custom Java structures like as Joglo and Limasan will grow each year as a result of this initiative.

According to interviews with the local director of PNPMM Mandiri Pariwisata Kotagede, Sarjono, indicated that the government program or donor-funded initiatives entered Kotagede during Yogyakarta's 2006 tectonic earthquake, which claimed countless lives and caused substantial damage to structures and dwellings. Kotagede, which is divided into two administrative districts by the Yogyakarta Municipality and the Bantul Regency, is home to several historic structures and was spared by the earthquake. As a result, from 2008 to 2010, the Javanese Reconstruction Fund (JRF) rebuilt damaged structures and established the Living Museum (in cooperation with the Ministry of Public Works' Directorate General of Human Settlements).

This initiative is being implemented as a result of collaboration between local governments and PNPMM Mandiri Pariwisata. The government would provide 65 million rupiahs through the PNPMM Mandiri Pariwisata over a one-year term. PNPMM Mandiri Pariwisata is organized into three sections: KSM Arts, culture, and history; KSM Culinary & Craft; and Purbayan Tourism Village, which combines all three. In 2012, as a continuation of the PNPMM Mandiri Pariwisata program, which residents successfully implemented within a year, Village Purbayan will get the second stage of the same aid program, with a 100 million allocation.

CONCLUSION

Specifically, the purpose of this study is to illustrate how stakeholders and the local community may collaborate to manage cultural and heritage places. Kotagede, in general, has a competitive advantage as a tourism destination since it has the ability to give tourists a broad range of cultural, historical, gastronomic, and architectural experiences that will appeal particularly to travelers interested in fragmented and living cultures.

Attractiveness and uniqueness of the Old Mataram Kingdom's history are the primary reasons for tourists to visit Kotagede. It is also aided by the ease with which it may be reached. Additionally, the silver handicraft branding in Kotagede contributes to the attraction of national and international tourists. We can observe from the building preserve that a large number of historical structures were destroyed in the 2006 earthquake, which prompted various fund agencies such as the Java Reconstruction Fund (JRF) to assist in preserving and conserving the damaged structures.

Additionally, not only by the government, but also by numerous local communities such as the Kanthil Society, the Joglo Forum, the Community Self-reliance Agency (CSA), the Kotagede Documentation Center (KDC), and the PNPMM Mandiri Pariwisata, who genuinely care about the preservation and conservation of Kotagede's heritage. Their contribution ensures that Kotagede's architecture and cultural treasures are saved, maintained, and sustained as tourism destinations.

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